

world, as it really grouped some of the characteristics of the tragic side of glory. Senhor Severo, like other Brazilians, had been before carried away by the balloon enthusiasm, but politics made him for a time lose trace of his fixed intent, when the Santos-Dumont tour of the Eiffel Tower came to awake his life's, or his death's, call. It was not jealousy, nor spite; it may have been competition, or emulation, but even that, by pure casualty or coincidence; it was another thing, it was the natural prompting, the inborn inspiration, set in motion by patriotic ambition. He was our second comer, and he thought he would increase, ten times, the natural asset created by Santos Dumont. I regret I am incompetent to deal with any of the scientific or practical merits of his balloon. There is only one point with regard to him upon which I can touch, and that is the noble sacrifice he offered, in his country's name, to the cause of Science. That sacrifice, whether you call it success or failure, we trust, will not remain sterile. Science advances mostly by the faith, the perseverance, the effort, the devotion of the common worker. The achievement, the invention, the stroke of genius or of luck, that form the visible personal contributions, are like everything else, the effect of the pressure from the circumference, the work of the same organic force that, at the proper time, shapes, hardens and ripens the results, like the fruits on the tree. One cannot make too much of imagination, which, alone, no doubt, possesses the creative touch; but one must make still more of the spirit of devotion and sacrifice, whence the kindling spark will ever come of the generosity that links together in the same chain the man who fails and the man who succeeds. The solidarity of success and failure, of finding and searching, of invention and routine, of steering and straying, of victory and disaster, is in the history of Science the necessary qualification of legitimate glory. It would be a sad day for Science when failure of a certain kind was not reckoned as secondary only to success. Ballooning, even now, seems among human achievements the one in which progress depends more on ever successive failures, if heroism and all its moral equipment can ever be called failure. We cannot as yet think of aëronautics as a science that could have been worked out to perfection at the proper time by the simple progress of mechanics, and without one single life being risked. But if such is to be the concept of the future, that would not render the disasters of the pre-scientific

times less honourable, and, perhaps, their legend would even grow, once closed the long martyrology of the air. The names written in it for the sake of progress and of Science, as well as of human ambition, like Andrée's or Severo's, will endure for ever. I honour our illustrious countryman's courage, his devotion, his thoroughness of purpose, his loftiness of ambition, his patriotic duel in the heights of the air with Santos Dumont, but above all I honour his fate. Men of that stamp will always be the pride of mankind, if, for nothing else, for their daring and for the kind of game at which they stake their lives. This is a sport of immortality. Last year the aëronauts of England honoured immortal success in Santos Dumont, to-day they honour immortal failure in Severo. It is because they know that, chiefly in their own career, in their deadly flight, failure and success are parts, fragments of each other, successive stages of the same successful evolution. I thank the Aëronautical Society for this demonstration. It is very flattering also, for us, that it met to-night to hear and to applaud a paper on Severo's invention by another Brazilian, Senhor Sampaio, a man of great mechanical and mathematical faculties. I am glad to hear from such authorities as we listened to to-night that the system deserves another test and that it will bear improvement. Senhor Severo's funeral in Rio de Janeiro, you will be gratified to hear, was of unprecedented national magnitude. That means we will remain attached as a nation to the great problem for which he laid down his life. Allow me to pay a finishing tribute of respect to his fate-companion, Monsieur Sachet, for his fearlessness and his disinterestedness, qualities that are inseparable from your noble calling, whatever its rank, but in no one so admirable as in those who have nothing to expect from glory. (Loud applause.)

Balloon Ascents in Thunderstorms,

BY THE REV. JOHN M. BACON.

Several authentic instances are on record of a balloon either approaching the neighbourhood where a thunderstorm is in progress, or of becoming actually enveloped in an active thunder pack. It is, however, to be regretted that these exceptional experiences have for the most part occurred to voyagers who, not being trained observers, have failed to furnish information of much practical or scientific value. All too obviously, for the most part accounts

have been overdrawn, an error to be extremely regretted both in the commercial as also in the scientific world. It is generally difficult to form a true picture or estimate of the phenomena recorded, and, perhaps, it would not be unjust to urge that all newspaper reports should be strictly estimated at their value as such.

A correspondent in the *English Mechanic* quoting from the *Canadian Weather Guide*, states that the aëronaut, S. A. King, ascended in August weather from Burlington, Iowa, just as a thunderstorm was approaching. When, in the moment of leaving the ground, his balloon was rapidly carried towards the thunderstorm, through which he was borne upwards. But instead of his piercing through the upper limits of the storm "there came down right in front of him, and apparently not more than 50 feet distant, a grand discharge of electricity." Then he felt the car lifted as the balloon was hurled through the cloud, and though it is not quite clear where he was hurled to, it is stated that fresh discharges of electricity kept doing the same thing over again till, finally—the most intelligible part of the narrative—heavy rain carried him down.

Again, the same correspondent, quoting from records, tells of M. le Moste ascending from Dunkirk on June 9, 1883, and being carried into a storm-cloud, where the "beating of the rain, the heavy gusts of wind, and the loud reverberations of the thunder, put the stability of the balloon to a fearful test." Here it would almost seem that the loudness of the thunder was thought to endanger the balloon.

But there follow equally extraordinary statements affecting a French aëronaut of European fame, M. Eugene Godard. Three journalists were his companions in an ascent during which "the balloon was caught in the middle of a thunderstorm, and twice the lightning flashed within a few yards of the terror-stricken crew." Surely it is the journalists here who are responsible for the statement!

Yet another quotation is given, and one which we may regard as of another order. It relates to a public ascent made at Frankfort-on-the-Maine by Green, junior, on August 22, 1847. The hour of departure was 5 p.m., and it appears that Green was determined to keep faith with the public, notwithstanding the fact that a thunderstorm was blowing up with a hurricane of wind from the south-west. When at about 4,500 feet elevation and level with the storm-cloud, the rain was descending like a waterfall. Each discharge of lightning caused a vibratory motion in the balloon. In

this instance the aëronaut succeeded in ascending above the storm, when a fine breeze from the north-west carried him clear of the disturbance.

It will be interesting to take the above narration in connection with a report on thunderstorms due to two eminent amateur astronomers, Prebendary Webb and Rev. T. E. Espin—the result of many years' research. According to these observers, when the thunderstorm is coming on the wind is usually blowing N.E., "or against the direction that the storm is coming from." Thunderstorms "come almost invariably from the south-west, and as soon as the storm has passed the wind will blow after it."

But quite as valuable a record is afforded by Charles Green, senior, in an ascent from Newbury in 1827. Green, describing the occasion himself, relates that the morning was very squally, and that the balloon could scarcely be kept down even with the strength of a hundred men. The force of the wind never abated, and when, at 6 p.m., the balloon was released, "it bounded off with great velocity in a S.E. direction, and in a very short space of time was riding the gale at a height of two miles. At this altitude we perceived two immense bodies of cloud operated on by contrary currents of air, until at length they became united, and at that moment my ears were assailed by the most awful and long-continued peal of thunder I ever heard. These clouds were a full mile beneath us, but perceiving other strata floating at the same elevation in which we were sailing, which, from their appearance I judged to be highly charged with electricity, I considered it prudent to discharge twenty pounds of ballast, and we rose half a mile above our former elevation, where I considered we were perfectly safe and beyond their influence. I observed, amongst other phenomena, that at every discharge of thunder all the detached pillars of cloud within the distance of a mile round became attracted and appeared to concentrate their force towards the first body of cloud alluded to, leaving the atmosphere clear and calm beneath and around us."

Charles Green's American contemporary, John Wise, describes a similar appearance of the storm-cloud as viewed from above. He compares it to a violent ebullition which soon developed itself into uprising cloud columns discharging flashes.

Very similar, again, is a description of Captains Peytier and Hossard in 1825; who, from the Peak D'Anie, in the Pyrennees, made

several observations of thunderstorms when these were in progress below, so that the upper surfaces were well seen. These surfaces were always noticed to be broken into ridges and protuberances, rising to great heights, like Alpine peaks.

But no more instructive instance of a thunderstorm observed from above is to be found than that reported last year in the *Journal of our Society*. I refer to the occasion when three lieutenants of the Prussian Balloon Corps made an ascent from Berlin on June 5, 1900. In this case the balloon was moving from the south-west at a height of 2,300 feet, when it became enveloped in a thunder-cloud. Sharp crackling sounds, as also loud hissings, were heard, accompanied by sparks, one of which was estimated as twenty-seven inches long.

Commenting on this storm, Dr. R. H. Scott points out that, though the thunderstorm at the time passed over Westphalia to the westward and over Pomerania to the eastward, yet no storm was experienced at Berlin underneath. And his explanation is that over the Valley of the Spree, the water being cooler than the air, there was a descending current of air which counteracted the normal ascending current of the squall, the consequence being that the thunderstorm was kept up and so jumped over the river. Dr. Scott adds, "the barometer at Berlin at the time showed the ordinary little jumps characteristic of the passage of thunderstorms, but no thunder or lightning was noticed in the city."

The following is an occasion when, during a balloon voyage from Newbury, I was unexpectedly enveloped in a severe thunderstorm, and remained for some time a close observer of the phenomenon. The date was July 27, 1900, a day which, opening with fair promise, became characterised shortly after noon by a succession of heavy electric storms, increasing in intensity and duration as the day wore on. Wind vanes remained pointing eastward, while cloud, at the height of some 2,000 feet, sailed away from the west. At less than this height, however, pilot balloons which started towards the west became headed back. The ascent was made at 5.15 p.m., at which time the clouds had all dispersed and the wind had lulled. Our course, which at first lay to the north and the north-west, turned nearly due west, and followed pretty closely the windings of the Kennet Valley.

It was about twenty minutes after the start that the air below us, and yet more ahead of us, began rapidly growing murky, while our

rate of progress became greatly accelerated. At this period no well-defined clouds were noticeable, our environment being veiled by the curtain of grey haze around; but from the starting ground at Newbury a vast thunder-pack was seen to be already upon us. Then the storm broke with a blinding sheet of hail, and a downrush of piercingly-cold air, the prelude to a terrific display of lightning, which flashed with great frequency and on all sides of us. Observers below informed us that we appeared to be embosomed in the heart of the storm, which completely enveloped us.

To ourselves, though the view overhead was hidden by the vast bulk of the balloon, it was evident that the flashes emanated from a region somewhat above our own level. Thus, to the eye, the manifestations of the lightning partook of the usual appearance, namely forked streaks of flame; but so bewilderingly brief and brilliant that the mind could scarcely determine whence they came or where they vanished. The thunder was no less remarkable, being short, with little rolling. It was clear that existing conditions stifled to us the usual reverberation; and this fact was confirmed by an experiment. Just as the storm was gathering I had fired a gun-cotton fog-signal below the car, and had remarked how the long-rolling echoes, always evoked, had been almost entirely quenched. Doubtless, then, the air was in extreme turmoil, either the cause or consequence of the electrical disturbance then being manifested. Broadly, the atmospheric conditions at this moment were a lower warm and now fast current still setting westward, an upper current bearing the storm-cloud diametrically opposed to the former, and, again, a swift, overmastering down-draught of ice-cold air, sweeping down the hail and carrying us towards earth.

A question arises here of much interest to aeronauts. Is a balloon entrapped in a thunderstorm in special danger of being struck by lightning? My own belief is that if it is being held captive by a steel cable the danger is extreme; and we heard of a fatal accident not long since to soldiers in charge of a military balloon kept flying while thunder was round. On the other hand, I do not fancy that special danger from lightning attends a free balloon if only from the fact that I know of no record of disaster, though balloons must have constantly ascended in thundery weather.

A feather or other floating body in the neighbourhood of an electrical machine in action is surely repelled rather than attracted. There is, however, of course, always the

possibility of a floating balloon being in a line of low resistance in which a discharge is preparing, in which case it would surely encounter such discharge.

After the reading of this paper, Mr. Bacon exhibited several lantern slides illustrative of his remarks, including a very fine series of photographs of lightning flashes.

Note on a Performance of the "Bristol" War Balloon during the South African Campaign.

BY CAPTAIN H. B. JONES, R.A.

[This communication formed part of a letter from Captain Jones, received from Machadodorp, Transvaal, by the Honorary Secretary.] It was read in the absence of Captain Jones by the Honorary Secretary.

"The 'Bristol' War Balloon, 11,500 cubic feet capacity, was first filled on March 6, 1900, the gas being transferred from 'Duchess of Connaught' leaking badly from bullet-holes received at Paardeberg. The balloon was up throughout the fight at Poplar Grove, and was emptied on March 9 without any repair in shops at the base; it remained on the section waggon until filled at Vet River (advance from Bloemfontein) on May 6. It was used at the engagements at Vet River and Land River, and arrived at Kroonstad on May 12. The balloon was kept in a sheltered place near the river till we marched again, on May 22, and was not emptied till after we had crossed into the Transvaal at Vereeniging on May 27. To keep a balloon going for 13 days at one station is a good test, but in our case the 'Bristol' was filled for 22 days, and did a march of 165 miles with the division.* It is unnecessary to say that this could not have been done with even a perfect balloon unless the weather had been good and the men of the section highly trained; it speaks wonderfully well for the fabric. The leakage was practically nil, but we occasionally had to run in some gas in the early morning to prevent the risk of towing a *ballon flusque* against the breeze which always came up with the sun, and later in the day we had to allow the expansion to run out. We had a very hard day the day before we crossed the Vaal, and I was inclined to empty the balloon, but the whole section were keen to get the 'Bristol' into Transvaal territory, and we did so. Our transport was oxen, slow but sure. We generally got into camp after dark,

and yet the men, tired with a long march, were always keen on doing everything they could to safeguard the balloon from the dangerous morning draught which caught her when she was slack and flapping."

Note on The Cycala Flying Machine.

BY DR. CHARLES ZIMMERMAN.

The ideal Flying Machine is the product of Nature, *i.e.*, the soaring-bird type. We have been endeavouring to construct a duplicate for nearly twenty years. We do not expect to realize our ideal, but we can approximate it and come nearer to it than if we had never tried. In our search for the secret of man-flight, at least half a dozen full-sized man-carrying machines have been built and experimented with, besides numerous models, each a different design, and like all other machines designed to navigate the air by other students and workers, failed to do more than get broken and smashed in pieces long before the testing was half completed. Enough, however, was gleaned to demonstrate that we were on the right track, and a little nearer the long sought-for goal. Still, we had not, as yet, discovered the key to the hidden truth, and it was necessary to do the same thing over again, making changes here and there, adding new improvements, until, at present, there is great encouragement to continue in the line of thought and experiment chosen, as it promises finally to produce what we are all looking for, and that, very soon.

The machine, "Cycala," now building, is about (35 ft.) thirty-five feet across tips of wings. The latter I propose to vibrate vertically, to get forward motion on the ground as well as in the air. I constructed a model of the same design as my machine. It was about eight feet across wing tips; during the past winter it was submitted to many trials, with the result that ultimate success is promised with a larger machine.

In all my trials with different models, I have concluded that it is a matter of getting the first start on the ground. The machine must lift itself from level ground; in order to do this, there must be primarily traction or propulsion *on the air*; the rest is, we surmise, comparatively easy. This, of course, presupposes that equilibrium and alighting or stopping are worked out. A bird jumps up and simultaneously flaps its wings at starting, and *begins to fly* when its forward speed is only a couple of miles an hour. Now, why should not a properly-constructed flying-

* It was at Fourteen Streams that a balloon worked continuously with one inflation during the late war. —ED.